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The Underwater Berlin Research Turbine: A Wind Turbine Model for Wake Investigations in a Water Towing Tank

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Abstract. The design of a three-bladed horizontal axis research wind turbine for wake investigations is described. The turbine has a rotor diameter of 1.3 m and will be operated in a large water towing tank at a submergence depth of 2.5 m, yielding 3.3% blockage. The test rig is configured to allow for underwater-stereo-particle-image-velocimetry measurements of the near and the far wake at chordwise Reynolds numbers approaching 700 000. The low-Reynolds number airfoil SG6040 is selected to constitute the rotor blades. Cavitation-free operation is assured by assigning a rated angle of attack of 1° . The blades are designed to maintain a constant circulation along the blade span and to minimize tip deflections. The blade pitch angles are adjustable. Various blade designs, with and without passive flow control devices, can be tested by replacing individual blade sections. This eliminates the need for multiple sets of blades. Sensors for acquiring the turbine's thrust, torque, rotational speed, the azimuthal positions of the blades, and the imposed blade root bending moments are incorporated into the design. The wind turbine simulation suite QBlade is utilized to simulate the turbine characteristics. A model of the entire test rig is derived, representing its structural properties. Results from the analytical verification of the structural model are provided. QBlade is utilized to analyze the test rig design by imposing design loads and calculating the modal properties.

1. Introduction

The wakes of horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs) extend up to 20 rotor diameters downstream. Wind speed drops to 20% of the undisturbed inflow velocity and increased turbulence intensities reaching 150% compared to the ambient level have been observed. Shadowed turbines produce up to 40% less power [1] and experience 200 to 300% increased fatigue loads compared to the upstream ones [2]. The near wake of HAWTs is dominated by strong, concentrated tip vortices, which shield the low-velocity region behind the turbine from mixing with the ambient fluid [3]. The excitation of unstable mode shapes of the emerging helix has been identified as a promising strategy to induce a premature wake breakdown and ultimately accelerate the recovery of the velocity deficit [4]. Active control methods employing pitch actuators, the rotor speed controller, or trailing edge flaps have been tested in the past [5–7]. Alternatively, passive control approaches represent robust and cost-effective opportunities to reduce wake effects. Various means have been tested to decrease the coherence of the tip vortices, including altered blade tip geometries [8] and global rotor asymmetries [9]. Most of the experimental setups employ turbines with diameters below 1 m in air [10] and 0.5 m in water [8], yielding maximum chordwise Reynolds numbers of 120 000. Increasing the Reynolds number by enlarging the HAWT models is limited by the test section size. Minimal

blockage ratios are aimed for to assure the undisturbed evolution of the flow around the rotor and its wake. However, even large-scale wind tunnels impose limitations. Studies with test sections measuring up to 4.2 by 4.2 m report blockages of 40 % with maximum chordwise Reynolds numbers of 257 000 [11]. Additionally, wake investigations in closed-loop wind tunnels are limited by the length of the test sections. Conducting the experiments in water towing tanks poses a way of mitigating these challenges [12]. The ratio of the kinematic viscosity of air and water is approximately 15. The Reynolds number is increased by the same factor when testing a model of identical characteristic dimensions. The same applies to the timescales of the emerging flow oscillations, easing the temporal resolution requirements of the dedicated data acquisition system [13]. The typical scales of towing tanks allow for the investigation of large models with blockage ratios below 5 % [14]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, only one series of towing tank experiments of HAWTs has demonstrated the capabilities of this method [12]. However, that study does not delve into details of the design process of the model. Due to the approximately 800 times increased density of water compared to the density of air, the loads acting on the model and its support structures are scaled accordingly. The assessment of structural loads to dimension HAWT models for underwater wake measurements is therefore vital.

This paper summarizes crucial aspects of the design of the Underwater Berlin Research Turbine (UBeRT) at the Technische Universität Berlin, supplemented by numerical considerations. The test bed comprises a three-bladed HAWT with a rotor diameter of 1.3 m that will be submerged and tested in the large water towing tank facility of the university. An underwater-stereo-particle-image-velocimetry (uSPIV) system for wake measurements at several downstream positions complements the test setup. The UBeRT will enable comprehensive studies on the efficacy of various passive and active wake control strategies for tip speed ratios (TSRs) between 3 and 10, inflow velocities ranging from 0.5 to 1.75 m s⁻¹, and chordwise Reynolds numbers approaching 700 000. The turbine and the tower are currently being built. Future experiments will be supported by high-fidelity delayed-detached-eddy simulations conducted at University of Stuttgart. First results from wake simulations are presented in Weislein et al. [15]. Section 2 describes the available towing tank and uSPIV system, located at Technische Universität Berlin. Section 3 covers substantial milestones of the design process of the turbine. Section 4 encompasses the numerical representation of the aerodynamic and structural properties of the test rig, which is essential to the test bed's design. The low-fidelity (unsteady) blade element momentum (BEM) features of the open-source wind turbine simulation suite QBlade [16] are utilized.

2. Test Facility

The UBeRT is designed for tests conducted in the 250-meter-long towing tank of the university, with a cross-section of 8 by 5 meters (width by depth, Figure 1a). A 25-ton carriage rides on two rails parallel with the still water level. A dedicated closed-loop controller actuates the motion of the carriage up to a maximum forward velocity of 12.5 m s⁻¹ and accelerations of ± 1 m s⁻². At a towing velocity of 1.75 m s⁻¹, the channel Froude number reaches 0.25. Transverse waves with a maximum wavelength of approximately 1.96 m are created. At a submergence depth of 2.5 m the particle trajectories induced by the surface waves have decayed sufficiently to not affect any model properties [12, 17]. Besides constant velocities and controlled acceleration ramps, the controller allows for sinusoidally modulated velocity profiles. Eight 55.5 kW direct-current motors provide the required power. Detailed insights into best-practice procedures to assure high data quality when conducting experiments in the facility are provided by Jentzsch et al. [17].

Figure 1: Test bed: a) Towing tank and carriage [17]; b) Turbine model, exemplary laser light sheet and field of view, and underwater-stereo-particle-image-velocimetry system.

Alongside the turbine, a watertight enclosure is towed through the tank (Figure 1b). It houses two 14-bit charge-coupled device cameras with a resolution of 1392 by 1040 pixels (width by height) for uSPIV measurements. Image pairs are recorded at a maximum frame rate of 5 Hz. The laser is emanating from the top to record streamwise sections. The laser head and the camera enclosure are rigidly connected to ensure an efficient calibration procedure. The entire PIV system can be translated in vertical and lateral directions relative to the turbine to change the position of the field of view. Measurements up to seven rotor diameters downstream of the turbine are enabled by traversing the HAWT in the longitudinal direction. The uSPIV system is triggered utilizing a saw-tooth signal, derived from the instantaneous blade phase. The proof of concept of the uSPIV system is provided in Schmidt [18] by comparing bluff body wake measurements with wind tunnel results.

3. Design Description of the Underwater Berlin Research Turbine

The UBeRT is a HAWT with a rotor diameter of 1.3 m. It is designed to be attached to the test platform of the tow carriage and thereby submerged into the basin to a hub depth of 2.5 m. A blockage of 3.3 % is obtained, promoting the free expansion of the wake of the turbine. The main design objective is for the turbine model to generate a representative HAWT wake. The design success is qualified considering the rotor characteristics and the circulation distribution along the blade axis. The work of Payne et al. [19] proved to be abundantly helpful during the design process of the turbine.

3.1. Airfoil Selection

The blades of the UBeRT are derived from the SG6040 airfoil (Figure 2a). The profile is characterized by a relative thickness of 16 %, located at 35 % of the chord. According to Lyon et al. [20], the airfoil is suitable for low-Reynolds number applications while offering a comparably large flapwise moment of resistance to limit blade tip deflections. For manufacturing reasons, the airfoil is gradually thickened, starting at the leading edge (Figure 2a, marked *Thick*). The function $y_T = y_S + 0.5\Delta x_c, \forall y_T \geq 0$ is utilized for the suction side, $y_T = y_S - 0.5\Delta x_c, \forall y_T < 0$ for the pressure side [21]. y_T denotes the y coordinate of the thickened profile at chordwise normalized location x_c , y_S the respective y coordinate of the original profile (Figure 2a, marked *Sharp*), and Δ the objective trailing edge thickness, in this case $\Delta = 0.01c$.

In Figure 2b, the lift polar derived from 2D experiments conducted by Lyon et al. [20] is displayed. The results are compared against XFOil simulations of the sharp and the thickened airfoil (experimental data marked *E*, simulations *X*). All presented data is generated with forced transition at $0.02c$ on the suction side and at $0.05c$ on the pressure side to reproduce the conditions of the experiments in Lyon et al. [20]. XFOil proves to be capable of reproducing the experimental data in the range of -7° to 5° . For larger angles of attack (AoAs), the maximum

Figure 2: a) SG6040 airfoil and utilized trailing edge treatment with edge thickness $\Delta = 0.01c$. Chord c ; b) Collection of lift coefficient data for SG6040: (E) Results of 2D experiments with tripping at $0.02c$ on suction side and $0.05c$ on pressure side reproduced from [20]. (X) XFOil simulations of depicted profiles with forced transition at same locations as in experiments. All data obtained at Reynolds number 400 000.

lift coefficient is overestimated. The thickening of the airfoil results in a larger slope and an increased maximum lift coefficient of 1.5 at 16° AoA.

3.2. Blade Design

In the process of designing the blade, special care must be taken to avoid cavitation throughout the entire parameter regime. For that, the minimum pressure coefficient of the airfoil at a given AoA is correlated with the local cavitation number [13]. Additional design objectives include a constant bound circulation along the radius, resulting in the generation of concentrated tip and root vortices, and a maximized chordwise Reynolds number are additional design objectives. The design AoA is 1° at rated conditions (TSR 7, inflow velocity 1.5 m s^{-1}) to meet these objectives. As for the Reynolds number and circulation, appropriate chord and twist distributions must be found [13]. Figure 3 displays the results of the blade design process. For $0 \leq r < 13 \text{ cm}$, the blade geometry is transitioned towards a circular blade root with a diameter of 5.7 cm. Two airfoils, interpolated from the SG6040 (Figure 2a) and a circular profile, are incorporated within the transition region. Dedicated sets of polars are derived with XFOil [13]. The blade chord is largest with 15.1 cm at $r = 15 \text{ cm}$ and decreases monotonically to 4.34 cm towards the blade tip ($r = 65 \text{ cm}$). The inflow angle varies along the blade span due to a linearly increasing tangential velocity. To meet the requirements of the design AoA, a blade twist ranging from 20 to 4.42° is defined. Figure 3 also shows the resulting flow state when operating the UBeRT at rated conditions. Over the center section of the blade ($25 \leq r \leq 50 \text{ cm}$), a constant bound circulation is achieved. Near the blade root and tip, the gradient of the bound circulation Γ increases, resulting in the formation of concentrated tip and root vortices [15]. The resulting inflow AoA is subject to larger variations, approaching 1° at $r = 30 \text{ cm}$ and dropping to negative values near the blade tip. At rated conditions, a chordwise Reynolds number at the tip of 400 000 is yielded. Up to a chordwise Reynolds number of 700 000, e.g., at inflow velocity 1.75 m s^{-1} and TSR 9, cavitation is not projected to occur. The model is designed to withstand loads up to an inflow velocity of 2 m s^{-1} [13]. Figure 4a shows the finalized blade design. It is composed of three sections to allow for interchangeable tips. The centerpiece is transparently displayed to highlight the section joints, consisting of tongue-groove-connections and centering pins (Figure 4a, marked 3). Each piece will be machined from a solid stainless-steel block on a 5-axis computer-controlled mill. Payne et al.'s [19] blade root attachment system for assuring a highly accurate, yet changeable blade pitch, is adapted and incorporated in the UBeRT blade design (Figure 4a, marked 2). This allows for reducing the spanwise AoA for off-design conditions. Especially at low TSRs, large AoAs up to 10° result, potentially causing stall and excessive loads [13].

Figure 3: Chord c and twist ϑ . AoA and circulation Γ at 1.5 m s^{-1} and TSR 7.

Tube type	Outer $\varnothing$	Inner $\varnothing$
Small	112 mm	90 mm
Large	200 mm	180 mm
Lower Bearing	120 mm	0 mm
Upper Bearing	135 mm	0 mm

Table 1: Dimensions of the tubular cross-sections of the tower.

3.3. Nacelle Design

The turbine components are placed inside a watertight nacelle (Figure 4b). O-rings, shaft seals, and IP68+-rated cable bushings ensure a safe operation. Additionally, water ingress detectors, a temperature sensor, and a triple-axis accelerometer are added for safety and monitoring. The nacelle is made from two tubes with different diameters: the front part has an outer diameter of 0.130 m and a length of 0.485 m; the rear part has a diameter of 0.155 m and a length of 0.985 m (both including the 3D-printed nose cones). A rotor-to-tower plane distance of 0.4 m is obtained. The total length of the nacelle is 1.560 m. The rotor-nacelle assembly, including the blades, weighs 84.72 kg. The total mass splits into 57.31 kg for all non-rotating parts, 13.04 kg for the rotating parts except the blades, and 4.79 kg for each blade. The rotational axis of the rotor is located 0.166 m below the turbine-tower connection.

3.4. Tower Design

The tower connects the tow carriage with the turbine and is composed of round tubes of four different cross-sectional profiles, denoted *small*, *large*, *lower bearing*, and *upper bearing* (Table 1). The segments are bolted together with the aid of welded flange pairings (Figure 4c). All tower members are made of stainless steel. The turbine is connected to a *small* tube of 0.829 m length (Figure 4c, marked 15). Scruton strakes will be attached to the small section to reduce the coherence of the tower's wake. The longest section of the tower has the dimensions of the *large* tube. The member, reaching from the *small* section to the hinge flange, is 2.285 m long (Figure 4c, marked 14) and pierces through the free water surface at 1.505 m (Figure 4c, marked 17). The submerged part of the tower can also be equipped with Scruton strakes. The hinge is located 0.78 m above the water level for installation and evacuation of the turbine. Another 0.188 m long *large* tower section spans the distance to the bottom of the tow carriage. At the lower bearing position, the tower is designed with a 0.200 m long *lower bearing* type profile (Figure 4c, marked 13). As for the upper bearing, a 0.128 m long *upper bearing* type cross-section is selected (Figure 4c, marked 11). The adjoining section has a *large* cross-section and a length of 1.331 m (Figure 4c). A pair of spherical roller bearings (*SKF 23024 CC/W33*), whose center distance measures 1.559 m is incorporated into the design to support the UBeRT test bed. The distance from the turbine connection flange to the center point of the lower bearing measures 3.402 m. The lower bearing floats, and the upper one is fixed. Additionally, at the lower bearing, the tower's rotation along the vertical axis is blocked by a brake. As shown in Figure 4c, marked 16, additional stiffening members can be installed to increase the structure's stiffness in specific directions if required or to tune the dynamic response of the

Figure 4: UBeRT turbine and test rig. **a)** Blade design based on SG6040 airfoil. (1) One of four strain gauge locations for measuring the blade root bending moments (BRBMs). (2) Disc for adjusting blade pitch, adapted from Payne et al. [19]. (3) Blade section joints. Centerpiece transparently displayed. **b)** UBeRT turbine. (4) Servo motor with planetary gear, rotor brake, and absolute multi-turn encoder for measuring the motor speed and the blade positions. (5) Three-component force gauge for measuring thrust and side forces. (6) Metal bellows coupling. (7) Floating shaft bearing. (8) Slip ring. (9) Fixed shaft bearing. (10) Strain gauge amplifiers for BRBM signal conditioning. **c)** UBeRT test rig. Truss system is attached to tow carriage (not displayed). Refer to Figure 1a for overall view. (11) Fixed tower bearing with streamwise brake. (12) Linear traverse for streamwise positioning. (13) Floating tower bearing with streamwise and rotational brake. (14) Large tower member. (15) Small tower member with Scruton strakes. (16) Exemplary stiffening rod. (17) Free water surface.

structure. Many more aspects of and additional insights into the design process, including the utilized decision-making methodology, can be found in Krumbein [13] and Krumbein [22].

3.5. Instrumentation

Each blade is equipped with root-bending moment sensors consisting of fully deployed Wheatstone bridges (Figure 4a, marked 1). *ME-Meßsysteme N2A-06-S5092R-350/E4* strain gauges are placed on the circular sections of the blades (Figure 4a, marked 10) in out-of-plane and in-plane directions. *ZSE Electronic ICA6H* strain gauge amplifiers condition the output signals for transmission to the data acquisition unit above water. These are placed inside the spinner of the turbine, just upstream of the rotor plane (Figure 4b). A partially hollow shaft allows for feeding the data through the hub into the nacelle, where a *Maverick Schleifring*

7KC000008 slip ring transforms the signals into the non-rotating frame (Figure 4b, marked 8). Two spherical roller bearings (*SKF 22206E* and *SKF 22205E*) support the main shaft (Figure 4b, marked 7 and 9). The drive train is complemented by a metal bellow coupling (*KB4K/200-60-32-24*, Figure 4b, marked 6), a 7.5 kW planetary gear motor (*SEW Eurodrive PSF522 CMPZ71M*, Figure 4b, marked 4), and an *SEW Eurodrive MDX61B0110-5-A3-4-00* frequency converter, placed on the tow carriage outside the water. An *AK1H* absolute multi-turn encoder resolves the turbine's rotational speed and blade positions for phase-dependent uSPIV triggering. The generated electrical torque provided by the converter is utilized to derive the turbine's power output. A three-component force gauge (*ME-Meßsysteme K3D120*, Figure 4b, marked 5), positioned between the tower and the turbine measures the thrust and side forces.

4. Numerical Assessment

Several modules of QBlade are employed to characterize the design of the UBeRT test rig, including BEM, modal analysis, and unsteady BEM (uBEM). For additional insights into the turbine's performance refer to Krumbein [22].

4.1. Model Description

A numerical model is derived and tested in the wind turbine simulation suite QBlade to qualify the test bed design. QBlade comprises full rotor design functionalities, including 360° polar extrapolation, blade design methodologies, and a steady BEM module to derive the turbine characteristics [16]. Unsteady BEM and lifting-line free vortex wake simulations are additional capabilities [23]. Full turbine beam models can be incorporated using the multi-physics software bundle Project Chrono [16]. Lately, QBlade's range has been extended by wave field solvers, enabling the simulation of floating offshore wind turbines and submerged structures [24].

The blade of the UBeRT is represented in QBlade by sets of 2D polars derived at various Reynolds numbers of the SG6040 airfoil and the two interpolated near-root airfoils. The twist and chord distributions, according to Figure 3, are accounted for. The cross-sectional properties of the blades are derived and provided in tabulated form [22]. The rotor model is complemented by a structural model of the nacelle and the tower. The masses, locations of the centers of gravity, and the moments of inertia of the rotor-nacelle assembly, excluding the blades, constitute the nacelle model. Euler-Bernoulli beam elements, defined by cross-sectional properties, are used to model the tower structure. Additional mass points representing the connection flanges are included. Hydrodynamic properties such as buoyancy or added-mass are omitted. Two nodes are placed along the tower's vertical axis according to the bearing positions, mentioned in Section 3.4. Their degrees of freedom are constrained accordingly (fixed-floating bearing pair with rotational brake at lower bearing position).

The validation of the structural solver is conducted by deriving two reference models and comparing QBlade's calculated static deflection due to a thrust force of 2220 N and the first eigenfrequencies. The results are summarized in Table 2. For the simplified model (Table 2, marked *Red.*) analytical solutions for the static tower deflection at the free end and the first two eigenfrequencies can be found [22]. This model is composed of a constant cross-section (Table 1, *Large*) along the whole length of the tower, constrained nodes at the bearing locations (Section 3.4), and a lumped mass at the free end equivalent to the rotor-nacelle assembly (Section 3.3). Only the first two side-side modes are compared with the QBlade results as the analytical model is two-dimensional. A more elaborate structural model is analyzed utilizing

Table 2: Results of the verification of QBlade's structural solver.

Model	Validation	Reference		QBlade	
	Method	Def. [mm]	Freq. [Hz]	Def. [mm]	Freq. [Hz]
Red.	Analytical	8.38	{7, 59.9}	8.25	{7.2, 56}
Full	Finite-Element	11.68	{6.2, 43.5, 125.1}	10.66	{6.9, 40, 90.3}

the finite-element functions of SolidWorks Simulation (Table 2, marked *Full*). It corresponds to the actual tower representation (Section 3.4) but omits all aerodynamic properties. Again, the nacelle and blade masses are lumped into one point at the end of the tower (Section 3.3). The model is three-dimensional. All modeling details, including the required tabulated cross-sectional properties, can be found in Krumbein [22].

Table 2 summarizes the results of the comparison of the tower deflection and the first eigenfrequencies (Table 2, marked *Def.* and *Freq.*). QBlade achieves a relative error of below 2% for the deflection and below 7% for the eigenfrequencies when compared with the analytical model. In that, the frequencies correspond to the first and second side-side eigenfunctions, respectively. The deviations of the results between SolidWorks and QBlade for the *full* representation are below 10% for the deflection and below 15% for the first two eigenfrequencies. QBlade achieves sufficient accuracy in estimating the frequencies but correlates them to deviating eigenfunctions. SolidWorks finds a coupled fore-aft and side-side mode at 6.2 Hz and individual side-side and fore-aft eigenfunctions both at 43.5 Hz. At 125.1 Hz, a side-side tower response of second order appears. QBlade however allocates individual side-side and fore-aft first order responses to 6.9 Hz, corresponding second order mode shapes to 40 Hz, and a fore-aft mode of third order to 90.3 Hz (Table 2). The deviating results could stem from the different treatment of the flanges and slightly different total model masses. For the design of the UBeRT test rig, QBlade achieves a sufficiently high accuracy in reproducing the results of the reference models.

4.2. Rotor Characteristics

The non-dimensional characteristics of the UBeRT are shown in Figures 5a and 5b for various inflow velocities throughout the parameter regime. For the simulations, the blades are discretized into 50 elements. Prandtl's tip loss model is included and the 3D-correction is switched on. The fluid density and the kinematic viscosity are set to 998.22 kg m^{-3} and $10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Both figures show a dependency of the obtained characteristics on the inflow velocity, likely due to Reynolds number effects. However, between the inflow velocities of 1.5 and 2 m s^{-1} , the curves converge. The power coefficient reaches 43% at TSR 6. The value represents an energy extraction comparable to modern multi-megawatt HAWTs. For higher TSRs, the power coefficient monotonically decreases towards 0. The power curves cross the abscissa at approximately TSR 12 for an inflow velocity of 0.5 m s^{-1} and at approximately TSR 14 for inflow velocities exceeding 1.5 m s^{-1} . The thrust coefficient approaches 83% at TSR 9 for an inflow velocity of 2 m s^{-1} , resulting in a thrust of 2200 N. For larger TSRs, the thrust coefficient decreases due to the reduced AoAs along the blade span (Figure 2b). The aerodynamic properties of the UBeRT reflect general characteristics and coefficients found in modern multi-megawatt turbines.

4.3. Modal Properties

QBlade's *modal analysis* tool is used to derive the eigenfrequencies of the non-rotating structural model. Several tower modes are revealed: two fore-aft modes at 6.6 and 31.3 Hz,

Figure 5: a) Power and b) Thrust coefficients for various undisturbed inflow velocities, derived from BEM simulations in QBlade. c) Campbell diagram: — Natural frequencies of first order fore-aft (FA1), side-side (SS1), and torsional (T1) response; — Integer multiples of the rotational frequency P ; (∇ , $\blacksquare$, $\bullet$) Selected operating points (tip speed ratio, undisturbed inflow velocity) coinciding with natural frequencies of the test bed.

two side-side modes at 6.6 and 35.9 Hz, and one torsional mode at 24.9 Hz. Rotor modes appear at 67.8 and 68.2 Hz (asymmetric and symmetric flapwise). Additionally, two combined modes are identified: a fore-aft tower mode with an asymmetric flap at 86.3 Hz and a side-side tower mode with a symmetric flap at 95 Hz. Figure 5c shows the Campbell diagram of the test bed up to rotational frequencies of 4.3 Hz (TSR 10, inflow velocity 1.75 m s^{-1}). The natural frequencies up to 30 Hz are vertically displayed. Selected integer multiples of the rotational frequency are represented by sloped curves. Operating points within the parameter regime, which intersect with the natural frequencies are highlighted. Considering the $1P$ excitation, the entire parameter space can be investigated without the risk of exciting structural frequencies directly. The $3P$ frequency, however, intersects at 2.2 Hz (e.g., TSR 6, inflow velocity 1.5 m s^{-1}) with the first order fore-aft (FA1) and side-side (SS1) tower frequencies, located at 6.6 Hz. The same is true for the $6P$ frequency at a rotational frequency of 1.1 Hz (e.g., TSR 9, inflow velocity 1 m s^{-1}). Another potentially dangerous operating point appears at, e.g., TSR 10 and inflow velocity of 1.7 m s^{-1} , resulting in a rotational frequency of 4.2 Hz, where the $6P$ curve meets the first torsional tower mode (T1). These operating points will be examined in particular during the commissioning of the test bed.

5. Conclusion

The crucial aspects of the design of a model HAWT (UBeRT) for extensive blade tip vortex and wake investigations in a large water towing tank at 3.3% blockage are presented. The SG6040 airfoil is selected to constitute the blade. The design AoA is aimed at cavitation-free operation throughout the parameter range. The design assures a constant circulation distribution along the span resulting in the generation of concentrated blade tip and root vortices. A dedicated drive train is tailored to the aerodynamic requirements. A properly dimensioned support structure, i.e., tower, connects the tow carriage and the turbine. Sensors for operational safety and turbine characterization are incorporated. The wind turbine simulation suite QBlade is used to characterize the design numerically. The rotor characteristics are presented. The turbine yields a maximum power coefficient of 43% at TSR 6 and a maximum thrust coefficient of 83% at TSR 9, both well within the range of modern multi-megawatt HAWTs. Combined with the replicated bound circulation distribution along the blade axis, the wake of the UBeRT will resemble wake features of modern HAWTs [15]. The turbine will therefore be suitable for wake measurements focusing on tip vortex instabilities and near-wake control. The aerodynamic model is supplemented by an analytically verified structural model for the

blades, the nacelle, and the tower. The numerical representation is analyzed regarding its eigenfrequencies to identify potentially dangerous operating points. The first two tower modes (fore-aft, side-side) are located at 6.6 Hz. The first rotor mode (asymmetric flapwise) appears at 67.8 Hz. The test rig is currently being built and will be commissioned during the first half of 2024. Measured characteristics, analyzed eigendynamics, and extensively quantified wake profiles will be acquired and published. Ultimately, the UBeRT test bed will provide detailed uSPIV wake measurements, focusing on wake breakdown mechanisms at chordwise Reynolds numbers approaching 700 000.

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References

- [1] Barthelmie R J, Pryor S C, Frandsen S T, Hansen K S, Schepers J G, Rados K, Schlez W, Neubert A, Jensen L E and Neckelmann S 2010 *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology* **27** 1302–1317 ISSN 0739-0572
- [2] Herbert-Acero J, Probst O, Réthoré P E, Larsen G and Castillo-Villar K 2014 *Energies* **7** 6930–7016
- [3] Crespo A and Hernández J 1996 *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* **61** 71–85 ISSN 01676105
- [4] Leweke T, Quaranta H U, Bolnot H, Blanco-Rodríguez F J and Le Dizès S 2014 *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **524** 012154 ISSN 1742-6588
- [5] Frederik J A, Doekemeijer B M, Mulders S P and Wingerden J 2020 *Wind Energy* **23** 1739–1751 ISSN 1095-4244
- [6] Brown K, Houck D, Maniaci D, Westergaard C and Kelley C 2022 *AIAA Journal* **60** 3298–3310 ISSN 0001-1452
- [7] Marten D, Paschereit C O, Huang X, Meinke M, Schröder W, Müller J and Oberleithner K 2020 *AIAA Journal* **58** 4672–4685 ISSN 0001-1452
- [8] Schröder D, Leweke T and Stumpf E 2023 *Experiments in Fluids* **64** ISSN 1432-1114
- [9] Abraham A and Leweke T 2023 *Springer Nature*
- [10] Lignarolo L E, Ragni D, Simao Ferreira C and van Bussel G G 2014 *32nd ASME Wind Energy Symposium* (Reston, Virginia: American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics) ISBN 978-1-62410-313-1
- [11] Soto-Valle R, Alber J, Manolesos M, Nayeri C N and Paschereit C O 2020 *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **1618** 032045 ISSN 1742-6588
- [12] Barber S, Wang Y, Jafari S, Chokani N and Abhari R S 2011 *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering* **133** 011007 ISSN 0199-6231, 1528-8986
- [13] Krumbein S 2023 Design of a horizontal axis wind turbine for experimental investigation in a large water towing tank Msc thesis Technische Universität Berlin Berlin
- [14] Larsson L, Hammar L, Nilsson L U, Berndtsson A, Knutson K and Danielson H 1989 *SAE Technical Paper Series* SAE Technical Paper Series (SAE International400 Commonwealth Drive, Warrendale, PA, United States)
- [15] Weislein T, Ferdinand S, Lutz T and Krämer E 2024 *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* ISSN 1742-6588
- [16] Marten D 2020 *QBlade: a modern tool for the aeroelastic simulation of wind turbines* Ph.D. thesis Technische Universität Berlin Berlin
- [17] Jentzsch M, Schmidt H J, Wozidlo R, Nayeri C N and Paschereit C O 2021 *Experiments in Fluids* **62** 1–20 ISSN 1432-1114 publisher: Springer; Springer Berlin Heidelberg
- [18] Schmidt H J 2018 *Drag Reduction of a Bluff Body Model in Water and Air* Ph.D. thesis Technische Universität Berlin Berlin
- [19] Payne G S, Stallard T and Martinez R 2017 *Renewable Energy* **107** 312–326 ISSN 09601481
- [20] Lyon C, Broeren A, Giguère P, Goopalarthnam A and Selig M S 1995 *Summary of low speed airfoil data vol 1* (Virginia Beach, Va.: SoarTech Publications) ISBN 978-0-9646747-1-4
- [21] Tucker Harvey S, Chen X, Rowe D, Bhavsar K, Allsop T, Gilbert J, Stallard T, Vogel C and Willden R 2021 *Proceedings of the 11th European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference* Number Of Volumes: 2276
- [22] Krumbein S 2023 Numerical Modeling of the Underwater Berlin Research Turbine in a Towing Tank Msc thesis Technische Universität Berlin Berlin
- [23] Saverin J, Peukert J, Marten D, Pechlivanoglou G, Paschereit C O and Greenblatt D 2016 *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **753** 082015 ISSN 1742-6588
- [24] Behrens de Luna R, Perez-Becker S, Saverin J, Marten D, Papi F, Ducasse M L, Bonnefoy F, Bianchini A and Paschereit C O 2023 *Wind Energy Science*